

Unfair trading practices in the agriculture and food supply chain – Some remarks on the Hungarian and German regulation

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Abstract

This paper aims to find an answer to whether unfair trading practices (UTPs) in the agriculture and food supply chain are of agricultural law or competition law in nature. Although the expression 'unfair trading practice' suggests that this phenomenon is treated within the framework and toolbox of competition law, beneath the surface other aspects of the issue may appear, if we examine such a specific area like agriculture and food supply chain. To answer the question, the author analyses some national aspects of the new EU directive on UTPs in the agriculture and food supply chain. A brief comparison is provided with regard to the possible direction of implementation in Hungary, in particular regarding the questions of scope ratione personae, scope ratione materiae, listed practices and sanction system. Besides this, a few aspects of the issue are also mentioned in connection with Germany. Before analysing the national questions, the author gives a short overview of the state of competition in the agriculture and food supply chain. In the end, a conclusion is drawn up based on the previous considerations, complementing them with further arguments that are not discussed in detail throughout the study.

Cet article vise à répondre à la question de savoir si les pratiques commerciales déloyales (PCD) dans la chaîne d'approvisionnement agricole et alimentaire relèvent du droit agricole ou du droit de la concurrence. Bien que l'expression "pratique commerciale déloyale" suggère que ce phénomène est traité dans le cadre et la boîte à outils du droit de la concurrence, d'autres aspects de la question peuvent apparaître sous la surface, si nous examinons un domaine aussi spécifique que l'agriculture et la chaîne d'approvisionnement alimentaire. Pour répondre à cette question, l'auteur analyse certains aspects nationaux de la nouvelle directive européenne sur les PTU dans la chaîne d'approvisionnement agricole et alimentaire. Une brève comparaison est fournie en ce qui concerne l'orientation possible de la mise en œuvre en Hongrie, en particulier en ce qui concerne les questions du champ d'application ratione personae, du champ d'application ratione materiae, des pratiques répertoriées et du système de sanctions. En outre, quelques aspects de la question sont également mentionnés en relation avec l'Allemagne. Avant d'analyser les questions nationales, l'auteur donne un bref aperçu de l'état de la concurrence dans la chaîne d'approvisionnement agricole et alimentaire. Enfin, une conclusion est élaborée sur la base des considérations précédentes, en les complétant par d'autres arguments qui ne sont pas abordés en détail tout au long de l'étude.

1. Introduction

This study aims to provide a brief analysis on some aspects of the regulation of unfair trading practices (hereinafter referred to as 'UTPs') in the agriculture and food supply chain. The article concentrates mainly on the Hungarian regulation, but it also mentions some developments in connection

with Germany. The impetus for the analysis comes from a new directive of the European Union¹ which intends to harmonise national legislations with regard to UTPs in agriculture and food supply chain. The Directive introduces a minimum Union standard of protection,² since UTPs in business-to-business relations „are addressed by national legislation through different legal instruments, sometimes overlapping and/or leaving issues or practices unregulated”.³ The existence of different regulatory approaches of Member States (hereinafter referred to as ‘MSs’) are strengthened by the literature. The classification of *Johan Swinnen* and *Senne Vandeveldde* differentiates four groups: MSs with no regulation, with private regulation, with ‘stretched’ legislation and with specific legislation.⁴ *Fabrizio Cafaggi* and *Paola Iamiceli* list the MSs into three types: they also have a group for countries with no legislation and specific legislation, but their third group is called limited scope legislation with mainly consumer-type UTP approach.⁵ Since „[t]here is a wide-spread consensus that UTPs occur throughout the food supply chain”,⁶ a legislative act aimed at creating harmonised regulation may contribute to handling a transboundary phenomenon, developing a more complete common market, as well as to economies of scale in administration and transaction cost savings.⁷

In general, this paper seeks to find an answer to whether the regulation of UTPs in agriculture and food supply chain are rather of agricultural law or of competition law in nature. For this purpose, the present article, firstly, gives a general insight into the state of competition in agriculture and food supply chain. Secondly, it mentions some aspects of the inapplicability of competition law when trying to control the UTPs of agriculture and food supply chain. Thirdly, it introduces the sector-specific regulation of Hungary, and sketches out a few aspects of the current German regulation. The paper provides a comparison of the Hungarian Act XCV of 2009 and the Directive with regard to the scope *ratione personae*, scope *ratione materiae*, prohibited practices and sanction system. The paper also presents a few aspects of the possible implementation of the Directive in Germany. Finally, a conclusion is drawn up in connection with both Member States and regarding the main question mentioned above.

2. The state of competition in the agriculture and food supply chain

The general reason for adopting the EU Directive is to alleviate the vulnerability of farmers and small and medium-sized agricultural enterprises to market conditions. The European Parliament, as early as in 2009, raised its concerns with regard to the food supply chain: (a) „large market power pays off in particular in the agri-food sector, given the price inelasticity of agricultural supply on the one hand and consumer demand on the other”; (b) „the trade sector makes use of its market power; including

¹ Directive 2019/633 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 17 April 2019 on unfair trading practices in business-to-business relationships in the agricultural and food supply chain (hereinafter referred to as ‘the Directive’).

² Directive, Preamble (1).

³ Study on the Legal Framework covering business-to-business unfair trading practices in the retail supply chain, Final Report, 26 February 2014, p. 69.

⁴ Johan Swinnen and Senne Vandeveldde: Regulating UTPs: diversity versus harmonisation of Member State rules. In: Federica Di Marcantonio, Pavel Ciaian (eds.): *Unfair trading practices in the food supply chain – A literature review on methodologies, impacts and regulatory aspects*. Luxembourg: Publications Office of the European Union, 2017, p. 44.

⁵ Fabrizio Cafaggi, Paola Iamiceli: *Unfair Trading Practices in the Business-to-Business Retail Supply Chain – An overview on EU Member States legislation and enforcement mechanisms*. Luxembourg: Publications Office of the European Union, 2018, p. 9.

⁶ Proposal for a Directive of the European Parliament and of the Council on unfair trading practices in business-to-business relationships in the food supply chain, COM(2018) 173 final, p. 1.

⁷ Swinnen and Vandeveldde, 2017, pp. 40–41.

excessive payment deadlines, listing charges, slotting allowances, threats of delisting, retroactive discounts on goods already sold, unjustified contributions to retailer promotion expenses or insistence on exclusive supply”; (c) „both the buying and the selling side of the market tend to be equally concentrated, thus aggravating the distorting effect over the market”.⁸ Ten years later, the Directive, in its preamble, strengthens these thoughts:

„Within the agricultural and food supply chain, significant imbalances in bargaining power between suppliers and buyers of agricultural and food products are a common occurrence. Those imbalances in bargaining power are likely to lead to unfair trading practices when larger and more powerful trading partners seek to impose certain practices or contractual arrangements which are to their advantage in relation to a sales transaction.”⁹

The basic situation is visible: there are market participants with superior bargaining power and there are those who are vulnerable to the previous ones.

This is not only true for the European Union. All over the world there are voices arguing against the industrialised food system because of its many anomalies. Basically and simply put, we can see the confrontation of two paradigms: an approach based on neoliberal political philosophy and neoclassical economics, which seeks to minimise state intervention in competition,^{10,11} and the paradigm of food sovereignty, which seeks to question each and every inherent feature of the industrialised food system, including the dominance of agribusiness, as well as the unfair trading system.¹² The neoliberal food system is the consequence of the ongoing structural transformation of agriculture in Europe and North America, dominated by some huge agri-food businesses.¹³ We also cannot forget the rise of supermarkets and hypermarkets in the second half of the 20th century. They have entered the market and totally changed it. Smaller producers are those who suffer the greatest losses, who, in general, may find themselves in a much more difficult commercial environment, given the demands of increased quantities and shorter deadlines.¹⁴

„The[ir] struggle to eke out a living has intensified each decade since 1950, because farmers have been locked into a system of low crop prices, borrowed capital, large debt, high land prices, and a weak safety net. Unchecked corporate mergers and acquisitions have increased the economic pressure, since fewer firms are competing to sell the seeds, equipment, and supplies that farmers use every day. At the same time, they have few choices where to sell their products.”¹⁵

⁸ Report of the European Parliament of 24 February 2009 on the food prices in Europe, (2008/2175(INI)), articles 12, 15 and 16.

⁹ Directive, Preamble (1).

¹⁰ Hope Johnson: *International Agricultural Law and Policy - A Rights-Based Approach to Food Security*. Edward Elgar Publishing, Cheltenham, 2018, p. 30.

¹¹ One of the three most important goals of economics (macroeconomics) based on neoliberal political philosophy is financial and trade liberalisation. See more: Joan Martínez-Alier, Roldan Muradian (eds.): *Handbook of Ecological Economics*. Edward Elgar Publishing, Cheltenham, 2015, p. 154.

¹² Alana Mann: *Global Activism in Food Politics - Power Shift*. Palgrave Macmillan, Hampshire, 2014, p. 3.

¹³ Peter Andree, Jeffrey Ayres, Michael Bosia, Marie-Josée Massicotte (eds.): *Globalization and Food Sovereignty - Global and Local Change in the New Politics of Food*. University of Toronto Press, Toronto, 2014, pp. 3–4.

¹⁴ Simon Maxwell, Rachel Slater: *Food Policy Old and New*. *Development Policy Review*, 2003, 21(5–6), pp. 535–536.

¹⁵ Wenonah Hauter: *Foodopoly - The Battle Over the Future of Food and Farming in America*. The New Press, New York, 2012, [e-book].

These structural changes go hand in hand with the concentration of market power, which neoclassical economics does not see as a problem to deal with, nor does it seek to capture the anti-competitive consequences of high market concentration and vertical integration.¹⁶ Although national competition laws and the effectiveness of competition enforcement differ significantly state by state, as well as countries are also different in how they deal with typical anti-competitive behaviour in the agriculture and food supply chain, such as cartels, abuses of dominant position or buyer power, but as a result of the development of the food system, the general structural changes causing concentration in the market are having an impact throughout the world. Fortunately, this was recognised in Hungary in time, and was also reflected in adopting Act XCV of 2009 at the level of legislation. It can also be said that not only the voices of neoclassical economists are heard in the European Union, and this is the reason that the Directive analysed in this study may have been adopted.

3. The Hungarian sector-specific regulation of UTPs and the case of Germany

3.1. Hungary

In this chapter the main focus is on the Hungarian regulation of UTPs concerning agricultural and food products, within the framework of which the national rules are compared to the provisions of the new Directive in some aspects. Both *Swinnen and Vandeveldel*,¹⁷ and *Cafaggi and Iamiceli*¹⁸ places Hungary into the group of countries with specific regulation, since – as already mentioned – Act XCV of 2009 regulates the prohibition of unfair distributors' practices against suppliers concerning agricultural and food products (hereinafter referred to as the Act). The Act came into force on 1 January 2010. We can see that the sector-specific UTP-regulation in Hungary has a past of more than ten years without any regulatory obligation coming from the European Union. The comparison includes the scope *ratione personae*, scope *ratione materiae* and some general features of prohibited practices.

Before analysing the Hungarian regulation, a key question has to be answered: why need specific regulation in connection with the anti-competitive issues of agriculture and food supply chain? Put simply, the set of instruments of competition law is not appropriate for handling this issue.^{19,20} Competition law instruments of the European Union, that is, the rules on the abuse of an undertaking of a dominant position (Article 102 TFEU) are not appropriate tools for this specific situation within the food supply chain. The market gets more and more concentrated. „Consolidation of food supply is increasing and more evident at every step of the food chain, from farm to fork.” [...] Of particular interest is the consolidation that is taking place at the level of supermarkets and retailers.”²¹ Nevertheless, based on the market shares of food retailers the conditions required for the applicability of Article 102 TFEU are not fulfilled. Not only the EU rules, but also the national rules on the abuse of the dominant position are not suitable, hence *sui generis*, specific norms are needed in order to handle

¹⁶ Valeria Sodano, Fabio Verneau: Competition Policy and Food Sector in the European Union. *Journal of International Food & Agribusiness Marketing*, 2014, 26(3), p. 162.

¹⁷ Swinnen and Vandeveldel, 2017, p. 44.

¹⁸ Cafaggi and Iamiceli, 2018, p. 9.

¹⁹ Firniksz Judit and Dávid Barbara: A versenyjog határterületei: a vevői erő régi és új szabályai. *Magyar jog*, 2020, 67(5), p. 277.

²⁰ Victoria Daskalova: The New Directive on Unfair Trading Practices in Food and EU Competition Law: Complementary or Divergent Normative Frameworks? *Journal of European Competition Law & Practice*, 2019, 10(5), p. 284–285.

²¹ Fair Trade Advocacy Office: *EU Competition Law and Sustainability in Food Systems: Addressing the Broken Links*, February 2019, Brussels, p. 23.

the imbalances of the food supply chain, because the restrictive and anti-competitive practices of giant food enterprises and retailers are not covered by the toolbox of classical competition law.

With regard to the scope *ratione personae*, there are a few differences that have to be mentioned. One difference is that there are no turnover thresholds determined by the Hungarian Act, while the Directive restricts its personal scope by setting up a cascading system based on the annual turnovers of suppliers and buyers.²² The assessment method of turnover thresholds differs from the approach of EU competition law, since the latter one „relies on market share thresholds combined with a qualitative analysis of market power”.²³ As stated above, the Hungarian Act does not even have an assessment method of turnover thresholds, nor does it limit its scope as the proposal of the Directive would have done. According to the proposal, the Directive would have applied only to certain unfair trading practices which occur in relation to the sales of food products by a supplier that is a small and medium-sized enterprise (SME) to a buyer that is not a small and medium-sized enterprise.²⁴ Although the Hungarian Act means a unique solution regarding the lack of (economic) assessment method, this does not raise any problem. Since the Directive aims minimum harmonisation, the Hungarian Act can maintain its current approach of not applying the assessment method of neither turnover and market thresholds, nor differentiating between SMEs and non-SMEs. As can be seen, in this aspect the personal scope of the Hungarian Act is broader than of the Directive, but this has no future implications.

Nevertheless, there is an aspect of scope *ratione personae* where the Hungarian regulation shall be brought into conformity with the Directive. The Hungarian Act only prohibits the unfair trading practices of distributors (retailers) against suppliers. In contrary, the Directive covers the unfair trading practices of all actors of food supply chain: not only of the distributors, but also of the wholesalers and processors against suppliers. It is already evident, if we look at their terminology. The Directive uses the word 'buyer' that includes any natural or legal person who buys agricultural and food products.²⁵ The Hungarian Act, as its title implies, refers to the practices of distributors, and covers only the relations of retailers and their direct suppliers.²⁶ This shall be amended in accordance with the Directive, because suppliers are not protected from the anti-competitive practices of all kinds of agents in the food supply chain based on the Hungarian regulation.

It can be concluded that the personal scope of the Hungarian Act is broader in one aspect (no turnover thresholds) and narrower in another one (covering only the practices of retailers) than of the Directive. Given the minimum harmonisation approach, the Hungarian Legislator does not have to change the Act's scope *ratione personae* in connection with the turnover threshold determined by the Directive, but has to expand the protection of suppliers even against the wholesalers and processors.

The scope *ratione materiae* is also different. The Hungarian Act refers to Article 2 of the regulation no. 178/2002 on laying down the general principles and requirements of food law, which says that 'food' (or 'foodstuff') means any substance or product, whether processed, partially processed or unprocessed, intended to be, or reasonably expected to be ingested by humans.²⁷ To this definition the

²² Directive, Article 1, 2. For example: This Directive applies to certain unfair trading practices which occur in relation to sales of agricultural and food products by suppliers which have an annual turnover not exceeding EUR 2 000 000 to buyers which have an annual turnover of more than EUR 2 000 000; suppliers which have an annual turnover of more than EUR 2 000 000 and not exceeding EUR 10 000 000 to buyers which have an annual turnover of more than EUR 10 000 000; etc.

²³ Daskalova, 2019, p. 282.

²⁴ Proposal for a Directive of the European Parliament and of the Council on unfair trading practices in business-to-business relationships in the food supply chain, COM(2018) 173 final, Article 1, 2.

²⁵ Directive, Article 2, 2.

²⁶ Firniksz and Dávid, 2020, p. 279.

²⁷ Regulation (EC) No 178/2002 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 28 January 2002 laying down the general principles and requirements of food law, establishing the European Food Safety Authority and laying down procedures in matters of food safety, Article 2.

Act adds that those products fall under its scope *ratione materiae* that – in order to be sold to the final consumers – do not require further processing.²⁸ According to the Directive, the scope covers agricultural and food products, which are products listed in Annex I to the TFEU as well as products not listed in that Annex, but processed for use as food using products listed in that Annex.²⁹ There are several differences in practice. Only two of them are mentioned here. For example, the Directive's scope covers all live animals, meanwhile the Act's scope does not cover live animals, unless they are prepared for placing on the market for human consumption. The Directive's scope covers unmanufactured tobacco and tobacco refuse, although the Act's scope does not cover tobacco and tobacco products. The conclusion is that, in order that the Hungarian Act be in accordance with the Directive, the Hungarian Legislator would need to change the Act's scope *ratione materiae*.

Concerning the most important part of the regulation, we can explore significant differences in connection with the list of unfair trading practices. In the Directive there are 15 practices listed: 9 of them are on the black list, so they are prohibited *per se*,³⁰ 6 of them are on the grey list, which are prohibited, unless they have been previously agreed in clear and unambiguous terms in the supply agreement or in a subsequent agreement between the supplier and the buyer.³¹ The Hungarian Act does not apply a differentiation like this. If we look at the way of formulation of the Directive's and the Act's wording, we can conclude that the Directive is formulated in a much more general way than the Hungarian Act. The regulation of the latter one is nuanced, more detailed with its 28 different unfair distributors' practices.

Without providing a detailed analysis of the comparison of listed practices, we can say that there are three practices in the Directive that cannot be corresponded to any of the unfair practices of the Hungarian Act. These are the following: (a) the buyer unlawfully acquires, uses or discloses the trade secrets of the supplier within the meaning of Directive (EU) 2016/943 of the European Parliament and of the Council;³² (b) the buyer threatens to carry out, or carries out, acts of commercial retaliation against the supplier if the supplier exercises its contractual or legal rights, including by filing a complaint with enforcement authorities or by cooperating with enforcement authorities during an investigation;³³ (c) the buyer requires compensation from the supplier for the cost of examining customer complaints relating to the sale of the supplier's products despite the absence of negligence or fault on the part of the supplier.³⁴

These practices shall be added to the Hungarian Act in order that it be in accordance with the Directive's minimum harmonisation approach. Although if we were permissive, a listed practice in the Hungarian Act may be appropriate for the third, above-mentioned practice (c). According to the Hungarian Act: it is unfair for distributors to require the use of services that are not requested by the supplier or that do not serve his/her interests, or to charge the supplier for these services based on any (legal) title.³⁵ One of the elements of the second practice, 'the threatening' appears in a practice listed in the Hungarian Act, nevertheless the prohibition in the Hungarian regulation refers to cases when the different types of threats take place in order that the distributor could reduce the purchase

²⁸ Act CXV of 2009, 2. § (2) d).

²⁹ Directive, Article 2, (1).

³⁰ Directive, Article 3, 1.

³¹ Directive, Article 3, 2.

³² Directive, Article 3, 1. (g).

³³ Directive, Article 3, 1. (h).

³⁴ Directive, Article 3, 1. (i).

³⁵ Act CXV of 2009, 3. § (1) ec).

price despite the protest of the supplier.³⁶ In my opinion, all the other 12 practices listed in the Directive can be found in some form in the Hungarian Act, therefore only minor amendments are needed in the latter one.

Concerning the sanction system, the Directive says that the Member States shall ensure that each of their enforcement authorities has the necessary resources and expertise to perform its duties, and shall confer on it the power to impose, or initiate proceedings for the imposition of, fines and other equally effective penalties and interim measures on the author of the infringement, in accordance with national rules and procedures. There are five other powers which are needed to be ensured for the enforcement authorities in favour of the efficient enforcement.³⁷ The Member States can establish their own sanction system that is suitable for their legal traditions, i.e. different sanction systems can coexist next to each other in the Member States. Let us look at a few characteristics of the Hungarian Act's sanction system.

It can be divided into two parts: first, if the enforcement authority, i.e. the National Food Chain Safety Office (an administrative body) finds an infringement, it may inform the trader before making a final decision that he can make a commitment statement within ten days to bring his conduct into line with the provisions of the law; second, if this does not happen, the enforcement authority imposes a fine. During the examined nine years, 206 infringements took place on the basis of public data: the majority of these can be considered as violations of substantive law, which are covered by the Act, Section 3(2), and there are some cases of procedural violations, typically failure to provide information. With regard to the total number of cases, we can conclude that the procedures were closed with the imposition of a fine in about 70% of the cases, while a commitment statement was made in about the remaining 30% of the cases. The data show that judicial review proceedings have been initiated in respect of 45 administrative proceedings, representing approximately 22% of cases. If we look at the level of fines imposed, it is clear that 2011 and 2012 stand out, as more than one billion forints of fines were imposed in both years. In 2013, it fell to approximately HUF 215 million, and only year 2015 (HUF 224 million) and 2016 (HUF 227 million) could approach it. In 2014, a record low total amount of fine of HUF 6.5 million was imposed. Starting from 2017 (HUF 81 million), a slow increase can be observed, as both 2018 (HUF 108 million) and 2019 (HUF 166 million) exceeded the previous years.³⁸

All in all, there are some changes needed in order to implement the EU Directive appropriately, but we can say that the fundamentals of the Hungarian Act are adequate. The enforcement mechanism works with the predominant feature of applying financial sanctions, i.e. fines. The EU Directive is not going to bring significant transformation in the Hungarian sector-specific regulation of unfair trading practices in the agricultural and food supply chain.

3.2. Germany

If we look at the regulation of Germany with regard to UTPs, a different approach can be recognised than of Hungary. Although *Cafaggi and Iamiceli* place Germany into the group of countries with specific legislation, they also note that „UTPs have been addressed by stretching the scope of competition law beyond the boundaries of Article 102 TFEU, and applying the concept of abuse to economic dependence or superior bargaining power.”³⁹ In this regard, *Swinnen and Vandeveld* do not consider stretching the existing legislation to be specific legislation; they set up a distinct group of countries

³⁶ Act CXV of 2009, 3. § (1) x).

³⁷ Directive, Article 6.

³⁸ Based on public data from <https://portal.nebih.gov.hu>.

³⁹ *Cafaggi and Iamiceli*, 2018, p. 9.

under the expression of 'stretched existing legislation'. It consists of not only Germany, but also Cyprus, Finland, Austria and Greece.⁴⁰ Without arguing for or against any of the classification above, it is manifest that both papers refer to the provision of § 20 (2) of *Gesetz gegen Wettbewerbsbeschränkungen* (GWB), which regulates relative market power and superior bargaining power. It is „the situation in which an undertaking has a market power not with respect to all other market participants (like in the case of a dominant position), but only with respect to another undertaking that economically depends on it.“⁴¹

Although there is no separate act in Germany to regulate UTPs in agriculture and food supply chain, there is a reference to food products in the above-mentioned paragraph of GWB. Companies with superior market power compared to small and medium-sized competitors may not use their market power to directly or indirectly hinder such competitors inappropriately. An unreasonable hindrance within the meaning of this sentence exists in particular if a company offers food products below purchase price, unless this is objectively justified in each case.⁴²

Without further analysis of current German legislation on UTPs of agriculture and food supply chain, it can be clearly stated because of the lack of specific legislation that the new Directive is going to bring significant changes within the regulation of the issue in Germany. This argument can be demonstrated by the fact that the implementation of the Directive is going to take place through a remarkable amendment of *Agrarmarktstrukturgesetz* (AgrarMSG).

According to the draft bill of the amendment,⁴³ *Agrarmarktstrukturgesetz* is going to be changed substantially. If accepted, it will be called *Gesetz zur Stärkung der Position des Erzeugers in der Lebensmittellieferkette*, i.e. Act on Strengthening the Position of Producers in the Food Supply Chain. Its abbreviated title will be *Lebensmittellieferkettengesetz* (LmlkG), i.e. Food Supply Chain Act.⁴⁴ The most relevant change for the issue analysed here is the new Part 3 of the AgrarMSG, which will include the provisions of the Directive nearly word by word. The draft bill also declares that the provisions of GWB, in particular its paragraphs 19 and 20 (abuse of dominant position and superior bargaining power), as well as the functions, powers and competences of *Bundeskartellamt* remain unaffected.⁴⁵ The enforcement authority will be the *Bundesanstalt für Landwirtschaft und Ernährung*, i.e. the Federal Institute for Agriculture and Food.⁴⁶

Two organisations, *Bundesvereinigung der Deutschen Ernährungsindustrie*⁴⁷ and *Deutscher Bauernverband*⁴⁸ have expressed their opinions on the draft bill. Without presenting their opinions in more detail, it is enough to mention that both organisations recommend further tightening of the rules, for example the practices of the grey list be handled as the practices of the black list, that is, the grey-list practices should also be prohibited *per se*. They emphasise that the word by word implementation is

⁴⁰ Swinnen and Vandeveld, 2017, p. 44.

⁴¹ Study on the legal framework covering business-to-business unfair trading practices in the food supply chain. Final report, Prepared for the European Commission, DG Internal Market, DG MARKT/2012/049/E, 26 February 2014, pp. 47–48.

⁴² GWB, § 20 Absatz 3, Nummer 1.

⁴³ Referentenentwurf des Bundesministeriums für Ernährung und Landwirtschaft: Entwurf eines Zweiten Gesetzes zur Änderung des Agrarmarktstrukturgesetzes.

⁴⁴ Ibid., Artikel 1, Nummer 1-2.

⁴⁵ Ibid., Artikel 1, Nummer 16.

⁴⁶ Ibid., Artikel 1, Nummer 7.

⁴⁷ Bundesvereinigung der Deutschen Ernährungsindustrie: Stellungnahme zum Referentenentwurf eines Zweiten Gesetzes zur Änderung des Agrarmarktstrukturgesetzes, Berlin, 6 August 2020.

⁴⁸ Deutscher Bauernverband: Stellungnahme zum Referentenentwurf eines 2. Gesetzes zur Änderung des Agrarmarktstrukturgesetzes, Berlin, 6 August 2020.

not enough, because the agreements appearing in grey-list practices are not drawn up as a consequence of the mutual consent of the contracting parties.

4. Conclusion

Our initial question of whether the regulation of UTPs in agriculture and food supply chain are rather of agricultural law or of competition law in nature can be answered as follows. After the adoption of the new EU directive, UTPs of agriculture and food supply chain are more in balance with the approach and characteristics of agricultural law than of competition law.

If we look at the case of Hungary, it can be seen that the Hungarian Legislator, ten years earlier than the adoption of the Directive, created a separate and distinct act, the Act CXV of 2009 which cut out the issue of UTPs in the food supply chain from the classical framework of competition law and from the competences of competition authority, and it authorised the National Food Chain Safety Office to act on the cases of unfair distributors' practices. The uprooting can also be strengthened by the literature: one of the Hungarian authors has characteristically declared that the Act CXV of 2009 is not placed within the „territory” of competition law.⁴⁹ It is manifest that the Act does not apply any established assessment method known from the toolbox of competition law. Tearing out the UTPs of agriculture and food supply chain from the world of competition law is also stated with regard to the Directive. According to *Victoria Daskalova*: „it [the Directive] is not a competition law solution”.⁵⁰

Through the example of Germany and its new draft bill, the same appears: a separate act (other than the traditional GWB) will regulate the UTPs of agriculture and food supply chain, and not a traditional enforcement authority of competition law will be authorised for dealing with these specific cases, but an authority of agricultural law, i.e. *Bundesanstalt für Landwirtschaft und Ernährung*.

If the expression ‘unfair trading practices of agriculture and food supply chain’ does not suggest that the phenomenon is treated within the framework of competition law, the question arises: on what grounds can we declare its agricultural law nature? Simply put, on the functional notion of agricultural law (*funktionaler Agrarrechtsbegriff*): according to this approach, agricultural law includes all provisions which have specific effects on agriculture (and forestry), not only if the given provision originates from a field of law characterised by „typical” agricultural interests, but also if the field of law in question is dominated by administrative purposes other than agricultural ones.⁵¹ The main interest and goal of the Directive is „to reduce the occurrence of [unfair trading] practices which are likely to have a negative impact on the living standards of the agricultural community”.⁵² It is also enshrined in the primary law of the European Union: one of the main objectives of the common agricultural policy is „to ensure a fair standard of living for the agricultural community, in particular by increasing the individual earnings of persons engaged in agriculture”.⁵³ Neither can it be forgotten that according to the Council Regulation No 1184/2006, „one of the matters to be decided *under the common agricultural policy* is whether the rules on competition laid down in the Treaty are to apply to the production of, and trade in, agricultural products”.⁵⁴ Without any doubt, unfair trading practices of the agriculture and food supply chain, which at first sight seem to be of competition law in nature, are fully connected

⁴⁹ Kocsis Márton: Vevői erő – a hazai szabályozás 8 éve és európai uniós kitekintés. *Versenytükör*, 2014/1, p. 66.

⁵⁰ Victoria Daskalova: Counterproductive Regulation? The EU's (Mis)adventures in Regulating Unfair Trading Practices in the Food Supply Chain, *TILEC Discussion Paper*, September 2018, p. 47.

⁵¹ Roland Norer (ed.): *Handbuch des Agrarrechts*. Wien: Springer, 2005, p. 4.

⁵² Directive, Preamble (1).

⁵³ Treaty on the Functioning of the European Union, Article 39, 1. (b).

⁵⁴ Council Regulation (EC) No 1184/2006 of 24 July 2006 applying certain rules of competition to the production of, and trade in, agricultural products, Preamble (2).

to the functional notion of agricultural law and therefore their scientific elaboration shall be performed by agricultural law experts.

Finally, another important aspect has to be mentioned. Why classify the legal relations in connection with food products to agricultural law and not to food law? Although according to the Regulation No 178/2002 of the EU, food law shall pursue, *inter alia*, the general objective of fair practices in food trade,⁵⁵ there are one more argument to be considered. *Ines Härtel and Dapeng Ren* note that „[a]gricultural law refers to the legal framework for agriculture”, and „[a]griculture is linked closely to the agribusiness”, meanwhile „food law refers to [...] the stages of distribution”.⁵⁶ Nevertheless, it cannot be forgotten that „[t]his legal separation of spheres has been losing its clarity in the face of more complex interfacing in the field of foodstuffs (agricultural products and further processed foods)”.⁵⁷ Given that agricultural law and food law are strongly intertwined, as well as that the main impetus behind the regulatory need is helping the agricultural community against agribusiness which is linked closely to agriculture, we can look at the UTPs of agriculture and food supply chain as a phenomenon of agricultural law in its nature. This concept of agricultural law also includes food law and thus the trade of food products. However, if one would like to also emphasise the role of food law because the functional notion of agricultural law is not accepted exclusively in this regard, we may formulate our conclusion by fully taking over the terminology of *Härtel and Ren*: the UTPs of agriculture and food supply chain are dominantly of *agri-food law* in their nature, and to a much lesser extent, of competition law.

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⁵⁵ Regulation (EC) No 178/2002 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 28 January 2002 laying down the general principles and requirements of food law, establishing the European Food Safety Authority and laying down procedures in matters of food safety, Article 5, 1.

⁵⁶ Ines Härtel and Dapeng Ren: Agri-Food Law: Term, Development, Structures, System and Framework. In: Ines Härtel (ed.): *Handbook of Agri-Food Law in China, Germany, European Union. Food Security, Food Safety, Sustainable Use of Resources in Agriculture*. Springer International Publishing, 2018, p. 3.

⁵⁷ *Ibid.*, p. 2.

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